

Neural network controller for five phases shunt active power filter applied for five phase embarked electrical network

Zakaria Laala¹, Amar Benaissa¹, Boualaga Rabhi², Mohamed Fouad Benkhoris³

¹Laboratory of Applied Automation and Industrial Diagnosis, University of Djelfa, Djelfa, Algeria

²Electrical Engineering departments, University of Biskra, Biskra, Algeria

³IREENA, University of Nantes, Nantes, France

Article Info

Article history:

Received Jul 17, 2022

Revised Jan 9, 2023

Accepted Jan 22, 2023

Keywords:

Active filter

Embarked electrical network

Five phases PMSG

Neural network ANN

Self-tuning filter

ABSTRACT

This paper discusses neural network ANN controller applied for five phase shunt active power filter. Three-phase shunt active power filters are widely studied, however in this paper we investigate to extend their application to five phase embarked electrical network. Two-level five phase inverter is used as a shunt active power filter to reduce harmonics and compensate reactive power injected by a five-phase diode rectifier. An artificial neural network controller has been used to regulate the DC side of the inverter, thereby contributing to the calculation of the reference harmonic currents on the one side and controlling the injected harmonic currents on the other. Self-tuning filter (STF) is used to calculate the reference current. By using STF allow to extract the voltage and current fundamental components in the α - β -axis directly without the use of a phase-locked loop (PLL). Simulation results shows that the ANN controller presents appreciable performances in references tracking and the proposed five-phase shunt active power filter provides a sinusoidal supply current in phase with the line voltage with low harmonic distortion.

This is an open access article under the [CC BY-SA](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-sa/4.0/) license.

Corresponding Author:

Zakaria Laala

Laboratory of Applied Automation and Industrial Diagnosis, University of Djelfa

Djelfa, M73M+HRV, Algeria

Email: zakaria.laala@mail.univ-djelfa.dz or zakariaala282gmail.com

1. INTRODUCTION

Multi-phase generators have been studied in embarked electrical network applications due to their appealing properties. Their high level of freedom, enables them to function in fault mode [1]. Their advantages over three-phase electrical networks such as reduction of torque pulsation, reduction of harmonic currents in the rotor, lowering phase current without increasing phase voltage, reduction current harmonics of DC link and more efficiency and more power in the same frame make them more attractive [2].

Five phase generators permanent magnet synchronous generator PMSG are used to generate power in such application as wind power generation, electric vehicles and embarked electrical network [3]–[6]. In order to obtain a desired output power (power quality and power factor), a series of power converters are required. The use of this converters increase harmonic injection in the system [7], [8]. The injection of this harmonics creates several problems, including increased generator losses and low power factor, therefore generating more heat [9]. Different mitigation solution passive filters; active power filters (APF) have been proposed and used [10].

In three-phase networks to reduce harmonics and compensate reactive power [11]–[13], active power filters (APFs) are widely used. Many studies and applications in this field have been performed in various research [14]–[17]. In the applications of active power filters (APFs) in three-phase electrical

networks in order to reduce harmonics and to compensate the reactive power. However, the extrapolation of their studies and application in five phase electrical systems remains minimal. This paper presented an investigation on the application of an APF in five-phase embarked electrical network.

The instantaneous power (p-q) theory and synchronous reference frame (SRF) are two famous methods that have been employed in [10], [18]–[20]. When mathematical models of systems are not available, NNs can design controllers if we have information about the behavior of the system in the form of input-output data. In order to optimize the processing of harmonic current detection time, several artificial intelligence-based algorithms have recently been employed. Artificial neural networks (ANNs), which have high speed recognition and learning abilities but a simple structure, have attracted a lot of interest over the past years. These networks have been used extensively in the power electronic components of both machinery and filters devices, where they have demonstrated their efficacy.

Artificial neural network ANN has used in different application for the active power filter such as the identification and calculate the reference courants [21]–[23]. However, this paper presented an investigation of a five-phase shunt APF to compensate the reactive power and to enhance the quality of the power in a five-phase embarked electrical network. Also, we employed in this work p-q theory and the self-tuning filter (STF) using an artificial neural network controller to regulate the DC bus voltage and to control the injected harmonic currents. Through computer simulations, the performance of the reference current generation techniques (STF) and the artificial neural network controller in the five-phase network has been evaluated. Simulation results shows that the ANN controller presents appreciable performances in references tracking and the proposed five-phase shunt active power filter provides a sinusoidal supply current in phase with the line voltage with low harmonic distortion.

The paper is organized as follows: section 2 deals with the research methods. Reference current calculation is treated in subsection 2.2. In subsection 2.3 neural networks ANN for the control of the shunt APF is presented. In section 3, the simulation results are shown and discussed. Finally, section 4 presents the conclusion of the work.

2. RESEARCH METHOD

2.1. System configuration

Figure 1, shown the configuration of the study system where five-phase diode rectifier is connected to the five-phase PMSG feeding an inductive load (R_d, L_d). The five-phase two-level VSI forms the five-phase shunt active power filter connected to the five-phase network as shown in Figure 1. Self-tuning filter (STF) is used to extract harmonics and provide reference currents. An artificial neural network ANN controller is used to regulate the DC bus voltage and to control the injected current. Reactive power is compensated and harmonic currents are reduced using the proposed five-phase shunt APF.

Figure 1. Configuration of the study system

Figure 2 shows the global Simulink model used, as shown it is composed of the PMSG model, the nonlinear load model and the model of the five-phase shunt active power filter APF. The detailed model of the APF five-phase shunt active power filter is shown in Figure 3. As shown, it is composed of a power calculation block, a reference current calculation block and an inverter control pulse generation block.

Figure 2. Model Simulink of the five phase APF

Figure 3. Detailed of the model Simulink

2.2. Reference current calculation

2.2.1. Equation in Concordia frames

The five-phase machines (original frame) can be projected into principal and secondary Concordia frames by applying the five-phase Concordia transformation [24].

$$[X]_{ps0} = [C_5][X]_{abcde} \tag{1}$$

$$[X]_{ps0} = [X_{\alpha p} X_{\beta p} X_{\alpha s} X_{\beta s} X_0]^T, [X]_{abcde} = [X_a X_b X_c X_d X_e]^T$$

Here $[X]_{abcde}$ are the phase voltage and the electromagnetic force (EMFs) of the PMSG generator. Were:

$$[C_5] = \sqrt{\frac{2}{5}} \begin{bmatrix} 1 & \cos(\frac{2\pi}{5}) & \cos(\frac{4\pi}{5}) & \cos(\frac{6\pi}{5}) & \cos(\frac{8\pi}{5}) \\ 0 & \sin(\frac{2\pi}{5}) & \sin(\frac{4\pi}{5}) & \sin(\frac{6\pi}{5}) & \sin(\frac{8\pi}{5}) \\ 1 & \cos(\frac{4\pi}{5}) & \cos(\frac{8\pi}{5}) & \cos(\frac{2\pi}{5}) & \cos(\frac{6\pi}{5}) \\ 0 & \sin(\frac{4\pi}{5}) & \sin(\frac{8\pi}{5}) & \sin(\frac{2\pi}{5}) & \sin(\frac{6\pi}{5}) \\ \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} & \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} & \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} & \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} & \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \end{bmatrix} \dots \text{and} \dots [C_5^{-1}] = \sqrt{\frac{2}{5}} \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 1 & 0 & \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \\ \cos(\frac{2\pi}{5}) & \sin(\frac{2\pi}{5}) & \cos(\frac{4\pi}{5}) & \sin(\frac{4\pi}{5}) & \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \\ \cos(\frac{4\pi}{5}) & \sin(\frac{4\pi}{5}) & \cos(\frac{8\pi}{5}) & \sin(\frac{8\pi}{5}) & \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \\ \cos(\frac{6\pi}{5}) & \sin(\frac{6\pi}{5}) & \cos(\frac{2\pi}{5}) & \sin(\frac{2\pi}{5}) & \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \\ \cos(\frac{8\pi}{5}) & \sin(\frac{8\pi}{5}) & \cos(\frac{6\pi}{5}) & \sin(\frac{6\pi}{5}) & \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \end{bmatrix} \quad (2)$$

2.2.2. Self-tuning filter

The work of Song Hong-Sock has allowed to establish a new form of extraction filter named STF. The fundamental components is extracted directly in the frame (α – β) as illustrated in Figure 4 [25]. The expressions relating the components (x̂_{αβ}) at the STF's output to the input components (x_{αβ}) are as follows, according to the axe (α-β).

$$\hat{x}_\alpha(s) = \frac{k}{s} [x_\alpha(s) - \hat{x}_\alpha(s)] - \frac{w_c}{s} \hat{x}_\beta(s) \quad (3)$$

$$\hat{x}_\beta(s) = \frac{k}{s} [x_\beta(s) - \hat{x}_\beta(s)] - \frac{w_c}{s} \hat{x}_\alpha(s) \quad (4)$$

Figure 4. STF principle

2.2.3. Harmonic isolator

In the case of five phase system the loads currents and loads voltages are transformed into principal and secondary Concordia frames (αp, βp – αs, βs) as (5):.

$$\begin{bmatrix} I_{\alpha p} \\ I_{\beta p} \\ I_{\alpha s} \\ I_{\beta s} \\ I_0 \end{bmatrix} = [C_5] \begin{bmatrix} I_{La} \\ I_{Lb} \\ I_{Lc} \\ I_{Ld} \\ I_{Le} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} V_{\alpha p} \\ V_{\beta p} \\ V_{\alpha s} \\ V_{\beta s} \\ V_0 \end{bmatrix} = [C_5] \begin{bmatrix} V_{La} \\ V_{Lb} \\ V_{Lc} \\ V_{Ld} \\ V_{Le} \end{bmatrix} \quad (5)$$

The load currents in the reference (α, β) are formed of two components a fundamental component and a harmonic component as (6)-(9).

$$i_{\alpha p} = \tilde{i}_{\alpha p} + \hat{i}_{\alpha p} \quad (6)$$

$$i_{\beta p} = \tilde{i}_{\beta p} + \hat{i}_{\beta p} \quad (7)$$

$$i_{as} = \tilde{i}_{as} + \hat{i}_{as} \tag{8}$$

$$i_{\beta p} = \tilde{i}_{\beta p} + \hat{i}_{\beta p} \tag{9}$$

Using the instantaneous power method (p, q) with STF, the detailed model of reference currents identification is shown in Figure 5. As shown, it is mainly based on the extraction of the fundamental components using the famous STF filter.

The following formulas can be used to represent the power components:

$$\begin{bmatrix} \tilde{p}_p \\ \tilde{q}_p \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \hat{v}_{\alpha p} & \hat{v}_{\beta p} \\ -\hat{v}_{\beta p} & \hat{v}_{\alpha p} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \tilde{i}_{\alpha p} \\ \tilde{i}_{\beta p} \end{bmatrix} \tag{10}$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} \tilde{p}_s \\ \tilde{q}_s \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \hat{v}_{\alpha s} & \hat{v}_{\beta s} \\ -\hat{v}_{\beta s} & \hat{v}_{\alpha s} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \tilde{i}_{\alpha s} \\ \tilde{i}_{\beta s} \end{bmatrix} \tag{11}$$

The reference currents in the (α, β)-axis is determined using the (12)-(15).

$$i_{\alpha p}^* = \frac{\hat{v}_{\alpha p}}{\hat{v}_{\alpha p}^2 + \hat{v}_{\beta p}^2} (\tilde{p}_p + p_c) - \frac{\hat{v}_{\beta p}}{\hat{v}_{\alpha p}^2 + \hat{v}_{\beta p}^2} \tilde{q}_p \tag{12}$$

$$i_{\beta p}^* = \frac{\hat{v}_{\beta p}}{\hat{v}_{\alpha p}^2 + \hat{v}_{\beta p}^2} (\tilde{p}_p + p_c) + \frac{\hat{v}_{\alpha p}}{\hat{v}_{\alpha p}^2 + \hat{v}_{\beta p}^2} \tilde{q}_p \tag{13}$$

$$i_{\alpha s}^* = \frac{\hat{v}_{\alpha s}}{\hat{v}_{\alpha s}^2 + \hat{v}_{\beta s}^2} \tilde{p}_s - \frac{\hat{v}_{\beta s}}{\hat{v}_{\alpha s}^2 + \hat{v}_{\beta s}^2} \tilde{q}_s \tag{14}$$

$$i_{\beta s}^* = \frac{\hat{v}_{\beta s}}{\hat{v}_{\alpha s}^2 + \hat{v}_{\beta s}^2} \tilde{p}_s + \frac{\hat{v}_{\alpha s}}{\hat{v}_{\alpha s}^2 + \hat{v}_{\beta s}^2} \tilde{q}_s \tag{15}$$

In the a-b-c-d-e coordinates, the filter reference current is defined as (16).

$$\begin{bmatrix} i_{fa}^* \\ i_{fb}^* \\ i_{fc}^* \\ i_{fd}^* \\ i_{fe}^* \end{bmatrix} = [C_5^{-1}] \begin{bmatrix} i_{\alpha p}^* \\ i_{\beta p}^* \\ i_{\alpha s}^* \\ i_{\beta s}^* \\ i_h^* \end{bmatrix} \tag{16}$$

Figure 5. Block diagram for instantaneous power (p, q) with STF

2.2. Neural networks ANN for the control of the shunt APF

In addition to producing currents to reduce undesirable harmonics or compensate for reactive power, the (SAPF) control strategy also requires recharging the capacitor to the value specified by the VDC voltage in order to assure proper power transmission to the inverter. Power fluctuations produced by harmonics, active power regulation, reactive power compensation, and converter losses are all absorbed by the storage capacity C. It is necessary to keep a steady average voltage across the terminals of the capacitor.

The aim here is to replace the conventional PI controller with an ANN controller. The ANN for controlling the dc bus voltage is illustrate in Figure 6. The input to the ANN block is the difference between the measured and reference DC bus voltages V_{dc} and V_{dc}^* . The proposed controller allows an appreciable dynamic, by absorbing or supplying active power on the electrical network, this voltage (V_{dc}) may beregulated.

Figure 7 shows the neural network-based injected-current controller. The input to the ANN block is the difference between the measured and reference compensation currents. The proposed regulator allows an excellent dynamic response, and the measured currents perfectly follow the reference currents as illustrated in the simulation results. Figure 8 shows the ANN controller structure for the DC bus voltage and injected current.

The following is a description of the ANN controller structure: i) Two hidden layers with six neurons that can activate in the Logsig and Tansig modes and ii) An output layer with a linear activation function. Scaled conjugate gradient backpropagation training is the method we used to train the ANN.

Figure 6. The use of the ANN to regulate the dc bus voltage

Figure 7. Injected currents control using ANN

Figure 8. Structure of the ANN controller

3. RESULTS DISCUSIONS

The configuration system parameters used in the simulation are detailed in the following Table 1. Figure 9 presents the five phase EMF supply voltage E_{abcde} of the five phase PMSG. According to Figure 10, the load current I_{La} (supply current I_{sa} without filtering) has a total harmonic distortion (THD) of 48.15%. In contrast, Figure 11 shows that under these conditions, the THD of the supply current I_{sa} after filtering is equal to 0.93%. The proposed neural network ANN control techniques enable simultaneous harmonic currents and reactive power compensation. The current injected by the five-phase shunt APF is shown in Figure 12(a). According to Figure 12(b), the obtained current and voltage waveforms are in phase.

A constant and ripple-free DC voltage has been imposed by the neural network ANN controller schemes that have been proposed. The system using an ANN controller under a step-change reference voltage V_{dc-ref} has been shown to have excellent transient and constant-state responses, as illustrated in Figure 13. According to the results, the technique based on neural networks has proven its effectiveness in achieving the objectives of controlling and tracking references.

Table 1. Simulation values

Parameters	Value	Parameters	Value
Supply frequency (Hz)	50	Filter inductor Lf (H)	0.01
Supply phase voltage Ea (V)	100	Filter resistor Rf (Ohm)	0.01
Stator resistance Rs (Ohm)	0.902	Load inductor Ld (H)	10e-3
Self-inductance L ₀ (H)	0.171 × 10 ⁻³	Load resistor Rd (Ohm)	10
Mutual inductances (M ₁)	0.021 × 10 ⁻³	Switching frequency	5 KHz
Mutual inductances (M ₂)	-0.078 × 10 ⁻³	Dc link capacitor C.dc (F)	350 e-6
Inductor Lc (H)	3.5 10 ⁻³	Vdc (V)	400
Resistor Rc (Ohm)	0.005		

Figure 9. Five phase EMF supply voltage

Figure 10. Supply current I_{sa} waveform without filtering

Figure 11. Supply current I_{sa} wave form after filtering

Figure 12. Injected active filter current I_{Fa} with ANN controller (a) power factor correction E_a and (b) I_{sa}

Figure 13. DC bus voltage V_{dc} under step change reference voltage

4. CONCLUSION

Five-phase shunt APF with neural network ANN controller under non-linear load and pure sinusoidal curve EMF profile conditions has been presented in this work. Also using five-phase PMSG as a generator allow to take advantage of multiphase embarked network such as fault-tolerant network for energy conversion. Reducing harmonics and compensation reactive power has been improved by using a modified version of the p-q theory to generate switching signals and optimizing the calculation of the reference current. STF filter allow to extract perfectly the fundamental components with no phase delay and with unity gain. The neural network ANN controller is developed to control the DC side voltage of the inverter and the injected reference current. Simulation results shows that the ANN controller presents appreciable performances in references tracking and the proposed five-phase shunt active power filter provides a sinusoidal supply current in phase with the line voltage with low harmonic distortion.

REFERENCES

- [1] L. Abdeljalil, M. Ait-Ahmed, and M. F. Benkhoris, "Singular perturbation modelling and control of embarked electrical network," *IECON Proceedings (Industrial Electronics Conference)*, pp. 454–459, 2006, doi: 10.1109/IECON.2006.347242.
- [2] S. M. Emil Levi, "Multiphase Electric Machines for Variable-Speed Applications," *IEEE Transactions on Industrial Electronics*, vol. 55, no. 5, pp. 1893–1909, 2008.
- [3] S. Rhaili, A. Abbou, S. Marhraoui, and N. El Hichami, "Vector control of five-phase permanent magnet synchronous generator based variable-speed wind turbine," *2017 International Conference on Wireless Technologies, Embedded and Intelligent Systems, WITS 2017*, 2017, doi: 10.1109/WITS.2017.7934647.
- [4] A. S. Abdel-Khalik, M. I. Masoud, and B. W. Williams, "Vector controlled multiphase induction machine: Harmonic injection using optimized constant gains," *Electric Power Systems Research*, vol. 89, pp. 116–128, 2012, doi: 10.1016/j.eprsr.2012.03.001.
- [5] L. Parsa, "On advantages of multi-phase machines," *IECON Proceedings (Industrial Electronics Conference)*, vol. 2005, pp. 1574–1579, 2005, doi: 10.1109/IECON.2005.1569139.
- [6] H. A. Toliyat, "Analysis and simulation of five-phase variable-speed induction motor drives under asymmetrical connections," *IEEE Transactions on Power Electronics*, vol. 13, no. 4, pp. 748–756, 1998, doi: 10.1109/63.704150.
- [7] M. I. Masoud, "Fully controlled 5-phase, 10-pulse, line commutated rectifier," *Alexandria Engineering Journal*, vol. 54, no. 4, pp. 1091–1104, 2015, doi: 10.1016/j.aej.2015.07.004.
- [8] M. I. Masoud, "Five-phase uncontrolled line commutated rectifier: AC side compensation using shunt active power filter," *2015 IEEE 8th GCC Conference and Exhibition, GCCCE 2015*, 2015, doi: 10.1109/IEEEGCC.2015.7060016.
- [9] J. Tsai and K. Tan, "H APF harmonic mitigation technique for PMSG wind Energy Conversion system," *2007 Australasian Universities Power Engineering Conference, AUPEC*, 2007, doi: 10.1109/AUPEC.2007.4548018.
- [10] A. Benaissa, B. Rabhi, M. F. Benkhoris, A. Moussi, and J. C. Le Claire, "Fuzzy logic controller for five-level shunt active power filter under distorted voltage conditions," *IECON Proceedings (Industrial Electronics Conference)*, pp. 4973–4978, 2012, doi: 10.1109/IECON.2012.6388986.
- [11] S. H. Mohamad, M. A. M. Radzi, N. F. Mailah, N. I. A. Wahab, A. Jidin, and M. Y. Lada, "Adaptive notch filter under indirect and direct current controls for active power filter," *Bulletin of Electrical Engineering and Informatics*, vol. 9, no. 5, pp. 1794–1802, 2020, doi: 10.11591/eei.v9i5.2165.
- [12] S. H. Qazi, M. W. Bin Mustafa, S. Soomro, and R. M. Larik, "Comparison of reference signal extraction methods for active power filter to mitigate load harmonics from wind turbine generator," *2015 IEEE Conference on Energy Conversion, CENCON 2015*, pp. 463–468, 2015, doi: 10.1109/CENCON.2015.7409589.
- [13] A. M. Hadi, E. M. Thajeel, and A. K. Nahar, "A novel optimizing PI control of shunt active power filter for power quality enhancement," *Bulletin of Electrical Engineering and Informatics*, vol. 11, no. 3, pp. 1194–1202, 2022, doi: 10.11591/eei.v11i3.3225.
- [14] Y. Sychev, B. Abramovich, and V. Prokhorova, "The assesement of the shunt active filter efficiency under varied power supply source and load parameters," *International Journal of Electrical and Computer Engineering*, vol. 10, no. 6, pp. 5621–5630, 2020, doi: 10.11591/ijece.v10i6.pp5621-5630.
- [15] Q. N. Trinh and H. H. Lee, "An advanced current control strategy for three-phase shunt active power filters," *IEEE Transactions on Industrial Electronics*, vol. 60, no. 12, pp. 5400–5410, 2013, doi: 10.1109/TIE.2012.2229677.
- [16] C. M. Thuyen, N. H. Thuong, and T. K. Tung, "Integrated compensation model using a three-phase neutral point clamped inverter," *International Journal of Electrical and Computer Engineering*, vol. 10, no. 5, pp. 5074–5082, 2020, doi: 10.11591/IECE.V10I5.PP5074-5082.
- [17] G. R., G. D. V. L., M. J., C. M., and M. J., "Model-based control for a three-phase shunt active power filter," *IEEE Transactions on Industrial Electronics*, vol. 63, no. 7, pp. 3998–4007, 2016.
- [18] A. S. Al-Ogaili *et al.*, "Time-domain harmonic extraction algorithms for three-level inverter-based shunt active power filter under steady-state and dynamic-state conditions-an evaluation study," *International Journal of Electrical and Computer Engineering*, vol. 10, no. 6, pp. 5609–5620, 2020, doi: 10.11591/ijece.v10i6.pp5609-5620.
- [19] A. K. Al-Othman, M. E. Al Sharidah, N. A. Ahmed, and B. N. Alajmi, "Model predictive control for shunt active power filter in synchronous reference frame," *Journal of Electrical Engineering and Technology*, vol. 11, no. 2, pp. 405–415, 2016, doi: 10.5370/JEET.2016.11.2.405.
- [20] I. Bessadet, H. Tédjini, and I. K. Bousserhane, "Hydrogen electrified railways based shunt hybrid filter," *Indonesian Journal of Electrical Engineering and Computer Science*, vol. 21, no. 3, pp. 1291–1298, 2021, doi: 10.11591/ijeecs.v21.i3.pp1291-1298.
- [21] M. Qasim and V. Khadkikar, "Application of artificial neural networks for shunt active power filter control," *IEEE Transactions on Industrial Informatics*, vol. 10, no. 3, pp. 1765–1774, 2014, doi: 10.1109/TH.2014.2322580.
- [22] S. Messalti, A. G. Harrag, and A. E. Loukriz, "A new neural networks MPPT controller for PV systems," *2015 6th International Renewable Energy Congress, IREC 2015*, 2015, doi: 10.1109/IREC.2015.7110907.
- [23] M. Rasheed, M. M. A. Alakkad, R. Omar, M. Sulaiman, and W. A. Halim, "Enhance the accuracy of control algorithm for multilevel inverter based on artificial neural network," *Indonesian Journal of Electrical Engineering and Computer Science*, vol. 20, no. 3, pp. 1148–1158, 2020, doi: 10.11591/ijeecs.v20.i3.pp1148-1158.

- [24] C. Liang, "Contribution à l'étude d'une chaîne de conversion d'énergie AC-DC/DC-DC tolérantes aux défauts," Thèse de doctorat en Génie électrique, 2017.
- [25] S. Hong-Sook, "Control scheme for PWM converter and phase angle estimation algorithm under voltage unbalanced and/or sag condition," PhD. in electronic and electrical engineering. South Korea, 2000.

BIOGRAPHIES OF AUTHORS

Zakaria Laala was born in Algeria in 1992. He obtained his Master degrees in Electrical Engineering from the university of M'sila in 2016. He works now his PhD degree from university of Djelfa. His research interests are on active power filter, FACTS, power system. He can be contacted at email: zakaria.laala@mail.univ-djelfa.dz.

Amar Benaissa was born in Algeria in 1968. He obtained his Engineer and his Master degrees in Electrical Engineering in 1992 and 2006 respectively, the PhD degree from the University of Biskra in 2014. His research interests are on uninterruptible power supplies and active filter. He is currently a researcher in LAADI Laboratory, University of Djelfa, as well as an assistant Lecturer, in Electrical Engineering Department, Djelfa University, Algeria. He can be contacted at email: benaissa_am@yahoo.fr.

Boualaga Rabhi was born in Algeria in 1969. He obtained his Engineer and his Master degrees in Electrical Engineering in 1992 and 1999 respectively, the PhD degree from the University of Biskra in 2008. His research interests are on uninterruptible power supplies. He is currently a researcher in MSE Laboratory, as well as an assistant Lecturer, in Electrical Engineering Department, Biskra University, Algeria. He can be contacted at email: boualaga@yahoo.fr.

Mohamed Fouad Benkhoris was born in Algeria in 1963. He obtained his Engineer in Electrical Engineering in 1992, the PhD degree from the University of Lorraine NANCY in 1991. His research areas are voltage regulation of multiple phase machines, the control and driving of electrical machines and renewable energies. He is currently a researcher in IRENA Laboratory, as well as a professor, in Electrical Engineering Department, Polytechnic Nantes, University of Nantes, France. He can be contacted at email: Mohamed-Fouad.Benkhoris@univ-Nantes.fr.